

Large-scale language models: challenges and perspective

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Abstract

The emergence of large-scale neural language models in Natural Language Processing (NLP) research and applications has improved the state of the art in most NLP tasks. However, training such models requires enormous computational resources and training data. The characteristics of the training data has an impact on the behaviour of the models trained on it, depending for instance on the data's homogeneity and size. In this talk, I will speak about how we developed the large-scale multilingual OSCAR corpus. I will describe the lessons we learned while training the French language model CamemBERT, the first large-scale monolingual model for a language other than English, especially in terms of the influence of size and heterogeneity of the training corpus. I will also sketch out a few research questions related to biases in large-scale language models, with a focus on the impact of tokenisation and language imbalance, in the context of the BigScience initiative. I will conclude with my thoughts on the future of language models and their impact on NLP and other data processing fields (speech, vision).

Bio

Benoît Sagot, Directeur de Recherches (Senior Researcher) at Inria, is the head of the Inria project-team ALMAnaCH in Paris, France. A specialist in natural language processing (NLP) and computational linguistics, his research focuses on language modelling, language resource development, machine translation, text simplification, part-of-speech tagging and parsing, computational morphology and, more recently, digital humanities (computational historical linguistics and historical language processing). He has been the PI or co-PI of a number of national and international projects, and is the holder of a chair in the PRAIRIE institute dedicated to research in artificial intelligence. He is also the co-founder of two start-ups where he uses his expertise in NLP and data mining for the automatic analysis of employee survey results.